

Invitation to Participate in the Survey: Labor Participation in Economy, Economic Well-Being, and Their Work-Life Balance (WLB) Following COVID-19 Outbreak

Assalamualaikum and Greetings,

We, the team of researchers from **Universiti Malaya (UM)**, **Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM)**, **Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM)**, and the **Institute of Labor Market Information and Analysis (ILMIA)**, are conducting research on labor participation in the economy, economics well-being and their work-life balance during COVID-19 pandemic.

Sincerely,

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